

ESTABLISHMENT OF COOPERATION BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND TURKEY

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Abstract: The article discusses the history of cooperation between Uzbekistan and Turkey.

Key words: Turkey, Soviet Union, Commonwealth of Independent States, Central Asia

In the early 90s of the 20th century, the disintegration of the USSR and the crisis of the socialist system led to the departure of the long-lasting "cold war" environment in international relations, the joining of the newly emerging young independent states to the world community, and the development of developed countries to strengthen their position in this region by establishing relations with them. entering into a mutually competitive, large-scale cooperation brought about fundamental changes in world politics, and it is no exaggeration to say that a completely new era in world history began.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, which achieved its national independence, the Basic Law of the country - the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted during this period, and based on world experience, a unique way of building a legal democratic state and civil society based on the market economy was developed. Recognized as the "Uzbek model", this path is aimed at the realization of the great goal of transforming Uzbekistan from an agrarian-industrial country to the ranks of developed countries in the world. The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, called this path in his work entitled "Uzbekistan - a great future country", saying: "We have chosen our path of independence and development, and this is the firm path of Uzbekistan."

In fact, due to the successful implementation of fundamental political, social and economic reforms in the republic, as well as the foreign policy based on the priority of national interests, equality and interest, Uzbekistan quickly came to the attention of the countries of the world, was drawn into the system of world economic relations, and in a historically short period of time, as an independent country, it took its rightful place in the world community. took its place. One of the factors of Uzbekistan's success is its international economic and cultural cooperation, as the President of the country I.A. organization of education on a large scale, all this is a very strong factor of economic reforms in the republic,

entering into world economic relations, and achieving a worthy position with equal rights in the world community.

This process was very difficult for Uzbekistan, which did not have its own foreign political state agencies, independent foreign policy and foreign economic activities, enough diplomats and experts in the field of foreign economic activities during the Soviet Union. In the words of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, "Independent Uzbekistan was forced to stand up and walk on its own on the day it was born."

In many laws adopted in the first days of independence, first of all, in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the legal foundations of a strong system implementing the foreign political activity of our country and its international cooperation were determined. The system of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan was fundamentally restructured. The Ministry of Foreign Economic Relations, the National Bank of Foreign Economic Activities and other institutions were established in our country. Embassies and consular offices of the Republic of Uzbekistan have been opened in many countries of the world. Departments and departments dealing with foreign economic activity and international cooperation were established in many ministries, state committees, concerns and banks of the republic. Turkey's economy developed rapidly in the last quarter of a century as a result of the transition to market relations based on the "Turkish model" of economic development associated with the name of the President of the Republic of Turkey Turgut Ozal (he was the president in 1989-1993). Sponsoring the development of the country's economy as a reformer of the state, attracting a large amount of foreign investments to the country, "export or death!" "Turkish model" was successful due to reorganization of production based on the slogan, and Turkey became one of the developed countries of the world.

Along with the countries of the world, Turkey also looks at the territory of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) as a newly opened market and has very close political and economic relations with the young independent states formed in this space, primarily with the Turkic-speaking countries with a close language, religion, and culture, in particular with Uzbekistan. , linked cultural ties. The English newspaper "Independent" compared the restoration of Turkey's relations with the countries of Central Asia to the fall of the "Berlin Wall".

Therefore, the entry of young independent Uzbekistan into the world community and its involvement in the integration process, in turn, Turkey's

aspiration to occupy a worthy position in the CIS region, is the necessity of the times, and this objective necessity created the basis for the establishment of mutual relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey. Of course, it is not for nothing that the relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey have developed rapidly and reached the level of large-scale cooperation. Because the Uzbek and Turkish peoples have established political, economic, cultural and educational ties for centuries.

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